

Digital Data vis a vis Right to Privacy in India

Varun Pratap Singh Bhakuni¹ & Nalnish Chandr Singh²

1. Research Scholar, Faculty of Legal Studies, Motherhood University, Roorkee
Mob. 9456190000 Mail: vps0006@gmail.com
2. Assistant Professor, Faculty of Legal Studies, Motherhood University, Roorkee

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Abstract

In the digital age, where personal data has become increasingly valuable and ubiquitous, the right to privacy has emerged as a critical concern. This research article explores the concept of digital data privacy in India, examining its legal framework, recent developments, and challenges. It explores important laws like the Sensitive Personal Data or Information) Rules, 2011 and the Information Technology (Reasonable Security Practices and Procedures) Rules, 2011, as well as the Supreme Court's seminal ruling in Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd.) v. Union of India, which upheld the fundamental right to privacy. The ramifications of digital monitoring, data breaches, and the function of public and private organizations in preserving individual privacy rights are all covered in this article. Additionally, it examines the impact of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and biometrics on data privacy. By analyzing relevant case studies and scholarly literature, this article offers insights into the challenges and opportunities for protecting the right to privacy in the digital era.

Key words: Digital Data, Privacy, Right to Privacy, Data Protection, India.

Introduction

In the current digital era, an unprecedented amount of personal data is being generated and collected due to the quick spread of technology. People contribute a lot of information online all the time, often without knowing how it is being used or safeguarded, on social media sites and e-commerce websites. This influx of digital data has raised significant concerns about privacy rights, prompting policymakers, courts, and civil society to reevaluate existing legal frameworks and practices.¹

"We are approaching the new era with 21st century technologies with 20th century governing processes and 19th century governance structures."

- *Harold A.Linstone*²

Interpretation and Explanation Since privacy is a multifaceted notion with many facets, it is better to list them than to define them. There is no agreement on what constitutes privacy in law or philosophy. A natural and inalienable right is privacy. Thus, rather than being given, it already existing. Respecting an individual is important, and it is not appropriate to disobey someone's wishes unless there is a very good reason to do so.

Since the term "privacy" is so ill-defined, it is impossible to define. It was first connected to enjoying one's possessions, but "over time it came to be seen as a necessary component for a person's individuality to blossom. J. Cooley says it just means having the freedom to live alone."³

The idea gained recognition after Warren and Brandies investigated the word in their article and traced the development of privacy law in the United States. In their "essay "The Right to Privacy", they defined that 'privacy' means a right to be let alone, and object of privacy is to protect 'inviolable personality'".⁴

The right to privacy is defined by "different jurists, sociologists, scholars in political science, technology, psychology concentrating on various aspects of the term 'privacy'". According to Salmond, "rights are interests protected by 'rules of right', i.e., by moral or legal rules."⁵ The term "natural right" refers to

interests that, "regardless of the existence or operation of a legal system, are morally defensible and hence entitled to protection". As a result, Roscoe Pound defines natural law as a theory of "moral attributes that are innate in humans and natural rights as inferences drawn from human nature by reason". "The right to privacy is a component of several legal systems that limit public and private conduct that jeopardize an individual's right to privacy."^{6,7}

In order for us to obtain these unique aspects of the right to privacy:

- (i) The freedom to have solitude is a right to privacy. It is a traditional turn on a negative right, according to which others have an obligation to keep out of your personal matters.
- (ii) A right in rem is the right to privacy. There is a right and a wrong in the world.
- (iii) A person's unalienable personality includes their right to privacy.

The Panel's report to the US President's office offers the most suitable definition as "Right of the individual to decide for him, how much he will share with others, his thoughts, his feelings and facts of personal life". Actually what is private varies from day to day and setting to setting.⁸

The European Union offers a beacon of guidance by enforcing the OECD principles for the protection of personal data and privacy, which are mandatory for all member nations. In order to safeguard personal information supplied to the government for specific services from being misused by commercial entities via service providers, the European Union released a new legislation in 1995. In 2018, a new legislation known as the General Data Protection legislation (GDPR) took the place of this one, further restricting the processing and transfer of data both inside and outside the European Union. It had made the way to several nations possible. India adopted computers and information technology somewhat later than the United States and Europe. The government saw the necessity to create the Information Technology Act, which was passed in 2000, in order to communicate in economic dealings with these nations. Despite the fact that this legislation was passed, privacy protection was not included. The aforementioned legislation was only passed in order to make business computer transactions easier. Although it was revised in 2008, it still does not guarantee or safeguard informational or personal privacy.

Research Objectives

Examine the current and existing legal framework to protect the right to privacy in India.

Research Methodology

This research is based on a critical and comparative analysis of worldwide legal systems, especially those that are in effect and mandated by relevant authorities, such as the United Nations Convention, the laws of the United States, the United Kingdom, the European Union, and India. These legal frameworks pertain to digital data and privacy. Because of the dynamic character of emerging technologies and their applications in highly regulated high-tech systems of governance and legal advancements, the study has its own limitations. Following tools will be used to achieve the objectives formulated for the present study:-

- i) International conventions, International and National Laws, Rules, Regulations etc.
- ii) Articles and journals
- iv) Reports of law commission and other agencies
- vi) Data collected by authentic agencies and relevant websites.

Legal Framework for Data Privacy in India

There isn't a unique law in India that addresses data privacy exclusively. Nonetheless, a number of laws and rules control how personal data is gathered, stored, and used in various situations. The Information Technology (Reasonable Security Practices and Procedures and Sensitive Personal Data or Information) Rules, 2011, which were released under the Information Technology Act, 2000, are among the important regulations.⁹ These regulations set forth standards for safeguarding sensitive personal information and mandate that organizations that handle it use appropriate security measures.¹⁰ In order to preserve data, India also joined the League of Nations. In 2011 and 2014, bills pertaining to

privacy were proposed. They had made provisions for individual privacy and data privacy. Biometric data protection was included in the Bill.¹¹ Yet, the parliament did not approve and finalize them. Additionally introduced were the Personal Data (Protection) Bill of 2013 and the Personal Data Protection Bill of 2018. Once more, though, the Parliament has not approved and ratified it.¹²

Privacy is crucial for the development of an individual's individuality. This personality is primarily made up of some inner qualities like freedom. Freedom and liberty lead to the achievement of autonomy of will. These fundamental principles form the foundation of each person's personality and identity, making them the most personal aspect of each. This core is distinct; it was built on secrecy and prospered in that environment. A privacy law relating to information technology should be self-contained, covering nearly all risks, violations, and encroachments over an individual's rights and interests, and it should be simply understandable by everybody.

The Indian Constitution now recognizes the right to privacy as a fundamental right, not just a common law one. The phrase "right to privacy" originates from two statements made in the Preamble, namely "liberty of thought, expression, belief, faith and worship" and "Fraternity assuring the dignity of the individual," as well as from Article 19 (1)(a)¹³ which gives to "every citizen a freedom of speech and expression and further emanating from Article 19(1)(d)"¹⁴ It, as stated in Article 21, grants each citizen "the right to move freely throughout the territory of India"; finally, the term "personal liberty"¹⁵. In fact, the freedom to privacy is inherent in these utterances, emanating from each one in turn and from their juxtaposition. Puttaswamy's J Abhay Manohar Sapre.¹⁶

The acknowledgement of privacy as an essential constitutional principle is a component of India's dedication to a worldwide human rights framework. The State shall make every effort to "promote respect for international law and treaty obligations in the dealings of organized peoples with one another," according to Article 51 of the Constitution, which is a part of the Directive Principles.¹⁷ The Universal Declaration of Human Rights acknowledges the right to privacy in Article 12. Comparably, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights' Article 17 was ratified on December 16, 1979, and it became operative on March 23, 1976. It was ratified by India on December 11, 1977, and it forbids both the protection of rights and such meddling and attacks. The ICCPR is referred to as a human rights document in the Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993, which was passed by Parliament. Human rights are defined in Section 2(1)(d). The National Human Rights Commission "is entrusted with the function of studying treaties and other international instruments on human rights and make recommendations for their effective implementation," according to Section 12(f) of the Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993. States are required by the ICCPR to uphold, respect, and adhere to its standards. "There is universal recognition of the fundamental importance, and enduring relevance, of the right to privacy and of the need to ensure that it is safeguarded, in law and in practice," according to a June 30, 2014, UN High Commissioner for Human Rights report. "Everybody has the right to respect for their home, their correspondence, and their private and family lives, according to Article-8 of the European Convention on Human Rights."

Judicial Recognition of the Right to Privacy

The judicial recognition of the right to privacy in India represents a significant milestone in the country's legal history, underscoring the importance of individual autonomy and personal liberty in the digital age. The genesis of this recognition can be traced back to the landmark Supreme Court judgment in Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd.) v. Union of India in 2017¹⁸, where the court unequivocally affirmed that privacy is a fundamental right enshrined within the ambit of Article 21 of the Indian Constitution, which guarantees the right to life and personal liberty. This watershed moment marked a departure from previous jurisprudence and laid the groundwork for robust privacy protections in India. The court's ruling emphasized the intrinsic value of privacy in safeguarding human dignity, autonomy, and freedom of expression, and recognized its role as a bulwark against state intrusion and arbitrary interference.¹⁹ The judgment resonated with global trends and established India as a trailblazer in the realm of privacy rights, inspiring legal reform and activism around the world. Subsequent judicial decisions and legislative measures have further bolstered privacy safeguards in India, including the enactment of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the

establishment of the Data Protection Authority (DPA) to oversee compliance and enforcement. However, challenges persist in effectively translating the right to privacy into practice, particularly in the context of emerging technologies, digital surveillance, and data breaches. The proliferation of surveillance technologies, mass data collection practices, and the absence of comprehensive data protection laws pose significant threats to individual privacy rights, necessitating ongoing vigilance and advocacy. Moreover, the intersection of privacy with other fundamental rights, such as free speech, equality, and due process, requires careful balancing and nuanced legal interpretation. As India navigates the complexities of the digital age, the judicial recognition of the right to privacy serves as a beacon of hope and a call to action for policymakers, lawmakers, and civil society to uphold and defend this fundamental right in all its manifestations. By safeguarding privacy, India can foster a more inclusive, democratic, and rights-respecting society, where individuals can exercise their freedoms and pursue their aspirations without fear of unwarranted intrusion or surveillance.

The necessity for data privacy regulations and the civil rights to privacy of every person, regardless of sexual orientation, sparked the privacy debate in the twenty-first century. A vital aspect of life and liberty, privacy is an inalienable component of the fundamental liberties guaranteed by the Constitution. It is present in "every person equally, regardless of gender, orientation, class, or stratum". It has a big impact on how someone develops their integrity, dignity, and personality. The right to privacy is not absolute, though, and any infringement must be justified by law and based on legitimate needs, proportionality, and the need to protect this valued right. Furthermore taking into account that we live in an "information-rich age where not all of the information we possess needs to be disclosed and requires specific protections and limitations, privacy plays a crucial role in this situation." In our "highly technologically advanced 21st century, the idea of protecting such privacy in the form of information is absolutely necessary."²⁰

Challenges to Data Privacy

Despite legal recognition and regulatory frameworks, data privacy in India faces numerous challenges. One of the primary concerns is the proliferation of digital surveillance by government agencies and private entities. Surveillance practices such as mass interception of communications and metadata collection raise serious questions about individual privacy rights and civil liberties. Additionally, data breaches and cyberattacks pose significant risks to personal data, highlighting the need for stronger cybersecurity measures and breach notification requirements. Some important points as below:

- Pervasive collection and aggregation of personal data by governments and corporations
- Lack of transparency and consent in data collection practices
- Commodification of personal data as a lucrative asset for data brokers and advertisers
- Cybersecurity breaches and data leaks leading to unauthorized access and exploitation
- Rapid proliferation of emerging technologies amplifying privacy risks
- Biased algorithms and invasive surveillance technologies perpetuating discrimination and eroding autonomy
- Varied regulatory frameworks and legal loopholes across jurisdictions
- Lack of awareness and digital literacy among users
- Intersection of data privacy with other societal issues like free speech and human rights
- Need for multifaceted approach combining technological innovation, legal reform, and societal engagement.

Emerging Technologies and Privacy Implications

Emerging technologies have brought about transformative changes in various aspects of our lives, revolutionizing industries, enhancing efficiency, and expanding possibilities. However, alongside the promises of innovation, these technologies also raise significant concerns about privacy implications and the protection of personal data. One of the most prominent examples is the rise of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning algorithms, which have become increasingly integrated into various applications and services, from predictive analytics to facial recognition systems. While AI

holds immense potential for improving decision-making, optimizing processes, and enhancing user experiences, it also poses risks related to privacy infringement, algorithmic bias, and loss of control over personal information. Biometric technologies, such as facial recognition and fingerprint scanning, raise concerns about surveillance, profiling, and potential misuse of sensitive biometric data. The Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem, comprised of interconnected devices and sensors, offers unparalleled convenience and connectivity but also introduces vulnerabilities and privacy risks due to the sheer volume of data generated and transmitted.²¹ Smart home devices, wearable gadgets, and connected appliances collect vast amounts of data about users' habits, behaviors, and preferences, raising questions about data ownership, consent, and security. Blockchain technology, heralded for its decentralized and immutable nature, presents novel opportunities for secure data storage and transactions but also introduces challenges related to privacy, anonymity, and regulatory compliance, particularly in the context of cryptocurrencies and decentralized applications. Virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies offer immersive experiences and interactive simulations, but concerns arise regarding data collection, tracking, and surveillance in virtual environments. Moreover, advances in genetic engineering, biotechnology, and neuro-technology raise ethical and privacy dilemmas related to the collection and manipulation of sensitive biological data, such as DNA sequences and brain activity patterns.²² As we navigate the complexities of the digital age, addressing the privacy implications of emerging technologies requires a comprehensive approach that balances innovation with accountability, safeguards individual rights and freedoms, and fosters transparent and ethical practices. Policymakers, industry stakeholders, and technology developers must work collaboratively to establish robust regulatory frameworks, implement privacy-enhancing technologies, and promote digital literacy and awareness among users.²³ By prioritizing privacy and data protection in the design and deployment of emerging technologies, we can harness the benefits of innovation while safeguarding individual autonomy, dignity, and fundamental rights in the digital era.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the right to privacy in the digital age is a fundamental aspect of individual autonomy, dignity, and freedom, and it holds immense significance in the context of India's evolving legal landscape. As technology continues to advance at a rapid pace, the protection of personal data becomes increasingly crucial to safeguarding citizens' rights and promoting democratic values. While legislative frameworks such as the Information Technology Act, 2000, and the Personal Data Protection Bill, 2019, represent important steps towards addressing privacy concerns, there remain gaps and challenges in their implementation and enforcement. It is imperative for policymakers, regulators, and stakeholders to work collaboratively to develop robust mechanisms for data protection, ensure accountability and transparency in data processing practices, and empower individuals with greater control over their personal information. Additionally, promoting digital literacy and awareness among citizens is essential to enabling informed decision-making and fostering a culture of privacy-consciousness in society. By upholding the right to privacy as a fundamental human right and integrating privacy principles into technological design and governance, India can strive towards achieving a more equitable, inclusive, and rights-respecting digital ecosystem for all its citizens..

Limitations of the Study

This research paper is especially limited to digital data and privacy in the present scenario due to limited resources and time.

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